

EFFECT OF WEIGHT TRAINING AND YOGIC PRACTICES ON EXPLOSIVE STRENGTH AMONG BASKETBALL PLAYERS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of weight training and yogic practices on explosive strength among basketball players. To achieve the purpose of the present study, forty five basketball players from Chennai, Tamilnadu, India were selected as subjects at random and their ages ranged from 18 to 24 years. The subjects were divided into three equal groups of fifteen each. Group I acted as Experimental Group-I (Weight Training), Group II acted as Experimental Group-II (Yogic Practices) and Group III acted as Control Group. The requirement of the experiment procedures, testing as well as exercise schedule was explained to the subjects so as to get full co-operation of the effort required on their part and prior to the administration of the study. This initial test scores formed as pre test scores of the subjects. The groups were assigned as Experimental Group-I, Experimental Group-II and Control Group in an equivalent manner. Experimental Group-I was exposed to weight training, Experimental Group-II was exposed to yogic practices and Control Group was not exposed to any experimental training other than their regular daily activities. The duration of experimental period was 6 weeks. After the experimental treatment, all the forty five subjects were tested on explosive strength. This final test scores formed as post test scores of the subjects. The pre test and post test scores were subjected to statistical analysis using dependent ‘t’ test and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to find out the significance among the mean differences, whenever the ‘F’ ratio for adjusted test was found to be significant, Scheffe’s post hoc test was used. In all cases 0.05 level of significance was fixed to test hypotheses. It was observed that the six weeks of weight training have significantly improved the explosive strength than the of yogic practices and control group.

Key Words: Weight Training, Yogic Practices, Basketball Players

Introduction:

Weight preparing enhances the muscle quality, power and perseverance. Particular weight preparing is to create particular quality of an occasion or a particular diversion. The investigation of yoga chips away at physical, mental, enthusiastic, clairvoyant and profound parts of a man. Yogic practice can help players to relax and replenish their energy after strenuous games. It also promotes calm, clear thinking even in situations that call for fast reactions.

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of weight training and yogic practices on explosive strength among basketball players. To achieve the purpose of the present study, forty five basketball players from Chennai, Tamilnadu, India were selected as subjects at random and their ages ranged from 18 to 24 years. The subjects were divided into three equal groups of fifteen each. Group I acted as Experimental Group-I (Weight Training), Group II acted as Experimental Group-II (Yogic Practices) and Group III acted as Control Group. The requirement of the experiment procedures, testing as well as exercise schedule was explained to the subjects so as to get full co-operation of the effort required on their part and prior to the administration of the study. This initial test scores formed as pre test scores of the subjects. The groups were assigned as Experimental Group-I, Experimental Group-II and Control Group in an equivalent manner. Experimental Group-I was exposed to weight training, Experimental Group-II was exposed to yogic practices and Control Group was not exposed to any experimental training other than their regular daily activities. The duration of experimental period was 6 weeks. After the experimental treatment, all the forty five subjects were tested on explosive strength. This final test scores formed as post test scores of the subjects. The pre test and post test scores were subjected to statistical analysis using dependent ‘t’ test and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to find out the significance among the mean differences, whenever the ‘F’ ratio for adjusted test was found to be significant, Scheffe’s post hoc test was used. In all cases 0.05 level of significance was fixed to test hypotheses.

Results and Discussion:

Table 1: Computation of Mean and Analysis of Covariance on Explosive Strength of Weight Training, Yogic Practices and Control Groups

	WTG	YPG	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Pre Test Mean	1.20	1.21	1.19	BG	0.002	2	0.001	0.50
				WG	0.07	42	0.002	

Post Test Mean	1.43	1.36	1.20	BG	0.41	2	0.20	145.14*
				WG	0.060	42	0.001	
Adjusted Post Test Mean	1.43	1.36	1.20	BG	0.41	2	0.20	145.66*
				WG	0.05	41	0.001	

* Significant at 0.05 level Table value for df 2, 42 was 3.21 and 2, 41 was 3.22

The above table indicates the adjusted mean value of explosive strength of Weight training, Yogic practices and control groups were 1.43, 1.36 and 1.20 respectively. The obtained F-ratio of 145.66 for adjusted mean was greater than the table value 3.22 for the degrees of freedom 2 and 41 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence. The result of the study indicates that there was a significant difference among the experimental and control groups on explosive strength. The above table also indicates that both pre and post test means of experimental and control groups differ significantly. The pre, post and adjusted post test mean values of explosive strength of both experimental and control groups are graphically represented in the figure 1.

Figure 1: Shows the Mean Values on Explosive Strength of Weight Training and Yogic Practices and Control Groups

Table 2: Adjusted Mean and Differences between the Means of Weight Training, Yogic Practices and Control Groups on Explosive Strength

WTG	YPG	Control Group	Mean Difference	CI Value
1.43	1.36	---	0.07*	0.03
1.43	---	1.20	0.23*	
---	1.36	1.20	0.16*	

Table 2 shows the adjusted means on explosive strength and difference between the means of the Weight training, Yogic practices and control group. The mean differences of Weight training group and Yogic practices group, Weight training group and control group, Yogic practices group and control group were 0.07, 0.23 and 0.16 respectively was greater than the CI value 0.03. Hence there exists significant difference.

Conclusion:

It was observed that the six weeks of weight training have significantly improved the explosive strength than the of yogic practices and control group.

References:

1. Manchanda, S. C. & Madan, K. (2014). Yoga and meditation in cardiovascular disease. Clin Res Cardiol. 2014 Jan 25.
2. Muthu Eleckuvan, R (2013). "Analysis of the changes in selected motor fitness components with concurrent strength and plyometric training", International Journal of Physical Education, Fitness and Sports; Vol.2. No.4, ISSN 2277-5447.
3. Nunes, P.R.P., Oliveira, A.A., Martins, F.M., Souza, A.P. & Orsatti, F.L. (2017). Effect of resistance training volume on walking speed performance in postmenopausal women: A randomized controlled trial. Exp Gerontol. S0531-5565(17)30378-9.

4. Senna, G., Salles, B. F., Prestes, J., Mello, R. A., and Simao, R. (2008). "Influence of two different rest interval lengths in resistance training sessions for upper and lower body", *Journal of Sports Science and Medicine*; 8, 197-202.
5. Seshagiri, N., Johnson, P., and Chittibabu, B. (2013). "Combined Effect of High Intensity Intermittent Training And Weight Training on Aerobic Capacity Anaerobic Capacity And Fatigue Index of Male Handball Players", *International Journal of Physical Education, Fitness and Sports*; Vol.2. No.4, ISSN 2277-5447.